

DESIGN AND CREATION OF THE AUTOMATED INFORMATION SYSTEM "REPUBLIC OF POPULATION REGISTRATION".

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ABSTRACT: In this master's thesis, the automated information system "Census of the Population of the Republic" was designed and a mobile application for a tablet was created in the Android Studio environment. The application was developed for the program that is expected to be held nationwide in 2025. The questionnaires filled out in the application are sent to the database of the Statistics Agency and processed there. The application works both online and offline.

KEY WORDS: Census, programming, respondent, Statistics, population, report, base, server, registration.

INTRODUCTION:

At the moment, the entire humanity feels the need for information and communication technologies, and at the same time, in our country, regular large-scale work is being carried out on the development of this field in the state administration, economy, social sphere, and its consistent introduction into the daily life of people.

In order to develop the digital economy in our country, IT centers have been established in all regions of our republic to enable our youth to acquire professions that are in high demand in the current labor market and to create conditions for the growing youth to meet the requirements of world standards based on their interests and abilities.

Research object and subject.

The object of the study is the population of Uzbekistan, the software and technical support bases produced. Datalogic method is used to control the flow of data for the study.

The subject of research is the population of Uzbekistan, the developed software and technical software "Census" system and the programs and technologies used in it.

The purpose and objectives of the research.

The purpose of the study - the main purpose of the census is to provide reliable and impartial information about the state of the population structure and the dynamics of development in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is necessary for determining and implementing the priorities of the state policy in the field of socio-economic and socio-political development of the country. consists of getting

Research task - Population census is a periodical process of collecting and processing data on a person, which determines the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the population, conducted in the entire territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan or in its specific regions.

System design using Algo UML

ArgoUML is an open source software for modeling and designing according to the UML (Unified Modeling Language) standard. UML is a structural, popular programming language and design language, and ArgouML allows you to create and analyze models according to these standards. The following information is about the capabilities of ArgoUML and the UML diagrams used:

Features: Cross-platform: ArgoUML is written in Java, so it is designed for most operating systems.

ArgoUML's source code is free and open source, and users can modify it according to their requirements and scope.

Argo UML has the ability to span multiple diagrams, each of which supports unique notations and algorithms that describe a specific aspect. A UML program consists of the following basic diagrams:

- 1 Use Case Diagrams: To show how the system interacts with other objects.
- 2 Class Diagrams: To organize classes, their attributes and methods.
- 3 Sequence Diagrams: To draw communication between actions and objects.
- 4 Collaboration diagram
- 5 Statechart Diagrams: To describe the states of objects.
- 6 Activity Diagrams: To show the sequence of activities.
- 7 Layout diagram.

Usage diagram. In this diagram, you can see a general model of the system usage process. This diagram shows the main roles in the system and the functions they can perform. In this diagram, you can see the process of using the

system by the 5 roles in the system: Chief administrator, management, developer, registrar and resident roles.

1-picture.Usage diagram

Class diagram. The initial model of the system base is created in the class diagram. This diagram models an overview of the tables that make up the data base. We work with tables and attributes in the data base through the class diagram. A class diagram is designed to describe the structure of information system software at the class level and their relationships to each other. A diagram shows classes, their attributes, their operations (methods, class functions), and relationships between classes (bindings). A class diagram for an entire information system containing all the classes developed would be very large, as some information systems may contain up to several thousand classes. Therefore, a class diagram can be created to solve one of the following problems. Using the class diagram, we create tables based on data, their attributes, and relationships between them.

2-picture.Class Diagram

The project was developed on the Android Studio platform:

3-picture. App in Android Studio

Main Screen :


```

package                                uz.xsoft.census.ui.screen
import                                android.content.Context
import                                android.net.ConnectivityManager
import                                android.net.NetworkCapabilities
import                                android.os.Bundle
import                                android.util.Log
import                                android.view.View
import                                uz.xsoft.census.MainActivity
import                                uz.xsoft.census.R
import                                uz.xsoft.census.presenter.impl.DashboardViewModelImpl
import                                uz.xsoft.census.ui.adapters.DashboardStatisticsAdapter
import                                uz.xsoft.census.utils.NetworkMonitor
import                                uz.xsoft.census.utils.extension.*

```

@AndroidEntryPoint

```

class MainScreen : Fragment(R.layout.screen_main) {
    private val navController by lazy(LazyThreadSafetyMode.NONE) {
        findNavController()
    }
    private val viewModel: DashboardViewModel by
        viewModels<DashboardViewModelImpl>()
    private val viewBinding: ScreenMainBinding by
        viewBinding(ScreenMainBinding::bind)
    private val adapter by lazy { DashboardStatisticsAdapter() }

    override fun onCreate(savedInstanceState: Bundle?) {
        super.onCreate(savedInstanceState)

        viewModel.openSurveyScreenFlow
            .onEach {
                navController.navigate(MainScreenDirections.actionMainScreenToScreenSurvey
                ())
            }
            .launchIn(lifecycleScope)
    }

    override fun onViewCreated(view: View, savedInstanceState: Bundle?) =
        viewBinding.bind {
            containerError.gone()
            viewModel.errorMessageFlow
                .onEach { showErrorMessage(it.getMessageString(requireContext())) }
        }
    }

```

```

        .launchIn(lifecycleScope)
viewModel.connectivityNetworkFlow
        .onEach {
        .launchIn(lifecycleScope)
NetworkMonitor.onNetworkStateChanged.observe(viewLifecycleOwner,
connectivityObserver)
listSections.adapter = adapter
buttonSurveys.clicks()
        .debounce { 100 }
        .onEach { viewModel.openSurveyScreen() }
        .launchIn(lifecycleScope)
buttonWebList.setOnClickListener {
    if (isOnline(requireContext())) {
        navController.navigate(R.id.itemFragment)
    } else {
        Toast.makeText(requireContext(), "Itimos internetni tekshiring !",
Toast.LENGTH_SHORT).show()
    }
}

```

CONCLUSION:

I used new literature and various information during the coursework I did on the topic of design and creation of the automated information system "Census" on the republic scale. I also got acquainted with programming technology. Compilation and creation of a census database is a necessary and important process for registration. The database provides the ability to combine, store, analyze and report data, which helps to effectively manage the performance of the registry.

Through the theoretical and practical part, the basic steps of database structure, creating tables and fields, entering and changing data, and creating the necessary queries were studied. These processes ensure the use of the data base and increase its efficiency.

Programming languages are the primary tools for creating and accessing databases. Their knowledge and skills ensure the effective management of the Census data base.

Finally, the creation and creation of a data base of pre-school educational institutions will help to manage the work of these systems in a qualitative and effective manner.

In addition, the creation and management of the population census database will greatly help the quality and efficient management of the census.

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